

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 91

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 91

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 91:1 He who dwells in the “shelter of the Most High Will abide in the ^bshadow of the Almighty. ² I will say to the LORD, “My “refuge and my ^bfortress, My God, in whom I “trust!” ³ For it is He who delivers you from the “snare of the trapper And from the deadly ^bpestilence. ⁴ He will “cover you with His pinions, And ^bunder His wings you may seek refuge; His “faithfulness is a ^dshield and bulwark.</p> <p>Psa. 91:5 You “will not be afraid of the ^bterror by night, Or of the “arrow that flies by day; ⁶ Of the “pestilence that ¹stalks in darkness, Or of the ^bdestruction that lays waste at noon. ⁷ A thousand may fall at your side And ten thousand at your right hand, <i>But</i> “it shall not approach you. ⁸ You will only look on with your eyes And “see the recompense of the wicked. ⁹ ¹For you have made the LORD, “my refuge,</p>	<p>Psa. 91:1 יִשָּׁב בְּסִתְרֵי עֲלִיּוֹן בְּצִלְ שָׁדַי וְתִלְוֶנָּה : ² אֵמַר לַיהוָה מִחֲסִי וּמְצוּדָתִי אֱלֹהֵי אֲבֹטְחָבוּ : ³ כִּי הוּא יִצִּילֵךְ מִפֶּתַח יָקוּשׁ מִדָּבָר הַמּוֹת : ⁴ בְּאַבְרָתּוֹ אִיסֵּךְ לֵךְ וְתַחַת־ כַּנְּפָיו תִּחְסֶה צְנֹחַ וְסַחֲרָה אֲמַתּוֹ : ⁵ לֹא־תִירָא מִפֶּתַח לַיְלָה מִחֵץ יַעוֹף יוֹמָם : ⁶ מִדָּבָר בְּאִפְלֵ יְהִלֵּךְ מִקְטָב יִשׁוּד צְהָרִים : ⁷ וְיִפֹּל מִצְדָּךְ אֵלֶיךָ וּרְבָבָה מִימִינֶךָ אֵלֶיךָ לֹא יִגָּשׁ : ⁸ רַק בְּעֵינֶיךָ תִּבְטַח וְשִׁלְמַת רְשָׁעִים תִּרְאֶה : ⁹ כִּי־אַתָּה יְהוָה מִחֲסִי עֲלִיּוֹן שָׁמַתָּ מְעוֹנֶךָ : ¹⁰ לֹא־תֵאָנֶה אֵלֶיךָ רָעָה וְאִנְגַע לֹא־יִקְרַב בְּאִפְלֵךְ : ¹¹ כִּי מִלְּאֲכָזִיז יִצְוֶה־לֵךְ לְשִׁמְרֶךָ בְּכָל־דְּרָכֶיךָ : ¹² עַל־ כַּפַּיִם יִשְׁאוּנֶךָ פֶּן־תִּגַּף בְּאַבְּן רִגְלֶךָ : ¹³ עַל־שִׁחַל וּפִתָּן תִּדְרֹךְ תִּרְמָס כַּפִּיר וְתַנְיִן : ¹⁴ כִּי בִי תִשָּׁק וְאִפְלִטְהוּ אֲשַׁגְּבֶהוּ כִּי־יִדַע שְׁמִי : ¹⁵ יִקְרָאֵנִי וְאֶעֱנֶהוּ עִמּוֹ־אֲנֹכִי בְּצָרָה אֲתִלְצָהוּ וְאֶכְבְּדֶהוּ : ¹⁶ אֲרֹךְ־ יָמִים אֲשַׁבֵּיעֵהוּ וְאֶרְאֶהוּ בִּישׁוּעָתִי :</p>

Even the Most High, ^byour dwelling place.

¹⁰ ^aNo evil will befall you,
Nor will any plague come near your ¹tent.

Psa. 91:11 For He will give ^aHis angels charge concerning you,

 To guard you in all your ways.

¹² They will ^abear you up in their hands,

 That you do not strike your foot against a stone.

¹³ You will ^atread upon the lion and cobra,

 The young lion and the ¹serpent you will trample down.

Psa. 91:14 ^a“Because he has loved Me, therefore I will deliver him;

 I will ^bset him *securely* on high, because he has ^aknown My name.

¹⁵ ^a“He will ^acall upon Me, and I will answer him;

 I will be with him in ¹trouble;

 I will rescue him and ^bhonor him.

¹⁶ ^a“With ¹a ^along life I will satisfy him
 And ²let him see My salvation.”

References

Psalm 91:0

^aPs 27:5; 31:20; 32:7

Psalm 91:1

^bPs 17:8; 121:5; Is 25:4; 32:2

Psalm 91:2

^aPs 14:6; 91:9; 94:22; 142:5

^bPs 18:2; 31:3; Jer 16:19

^cPs 25:2; 56:4

Psalm 91:3

^aPs 124:7; Prov 6:5

^{b1} Kin 8:37; 2 Chr 20:9; Ps 91:6

Psalm 91:4

^aIs 51:16

^bPs 17:8; 36:7; 57:1; 63:7

^cPs 40:11

^aPs 35:2

Psalm 91:5

^aJob 5:19-23; Ps 23:4; 27:1

^bSong 3:8

^cPs 64:4

Psalm 91:6

¹Or *walks*

^{a2} Kin 19:35; Ps 91:10

^bJob 5:22

Psalm 91:7

^aGen 7:23; Josh 14:10

Psalm 91:8

^aPs 37:34; 58:10

Psalm 91:9

¹Or *For You O LORD are my Refuge; You have made the Most High your dwelling place*

^aPs 91:2

^bPs 90:1

Psalm 91:10

¹Or *dwelling*

^aProv 12:21

Psalm 91:11

^aPs 34:7; Matt 4:6; Luke 4:10, 11; Heb 1:14

Psalm 91:12

^aMatt 4:6; Luke 4:11

Psalm 91:13

¹Or *dragon*

^aJudg 14:6; Dan 6:22; Luke 10:19

Psalm 91:14

^aPs 145:20

^bPs 59:1

^cPs 9:10

Psalm 91:15

¹Or *distress*

^aJob 12:4; Ps 50:15

^{b1} Sam 2:30; John 12:26

Psalm 91:16

¹Lit *length of days*

²Or *cause him to feast his eyes on*

^aDeut 6:2; Ps 21:4; Prov 3:1, 2

^bPs 50:23^aPs 83:18; 93:4; 113:5

Targum

Psa. 92:1 A psalm and song that the first Adam uttered concerning the Sabbath day. ² It is good to give thanks in the presence of the LORD, and to praise your name, O Most High. ³ To recount your goodness in the morning, and your truth in the nights, ⁴ According to the harp of ten strings, and according to the lyre, upon the murmuring of harps. ⁵ For you have made me glad, O LORD, by your works; I will rejoice in the works of your hands. ⁶ How great are your works, O LORD; your thoughts are very deep. ⁷ A foolish son of man will not know it, and a fool will not comprehend this. ⁸ While the wicked flourish like grass and all workers of deceit blossom, God is going to destroy them forever. ⁹ But you are high and supreme in this age, O LORD, and you are high and supreme in the age to come. [ANOTHER TARGUM: And you, your hand is supreme to punish the wicked in the age to come, in the great day of judgment, O LORD; and you, your hand is supreme to give a good reward to the righteous in the age to come, O LORD.] ¹⁰ For, behold, your enemies, O LORD, for behold, your enemies will perish in the age to come; and all the workers of deceit will be separated from the band of the righteous. ¹¹ You have raised up my might like a wild-ox; you have anointed me with moist anointing oil of the leafy olive. ¹² And my eye has looked on the perdition of my oppressors; my ear has heard the sound of the destruction of those who stand against me to do harm. ¹³ The righteous man will grow fruit like the palm-tree, like the cedar in Lebanon he will grow and produce roots. ¹⁴ His sons will be planted in the sanctuary of the LORD; in the court of the house of our God they will flourish. ¹⁵ Again like their fathers they will produce sons in old age; they will be plump and juicy. ¹⁶ So that the inhabitants of the earth might tell it, for the LORD is upright; my strength, and there is no wrong in him.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This Psalm was composed by Moses and dedicated to the Levites. The Levites dwelled in the shadow of the LORD because they spent their days in the insulated and sacred environment of the Tabernacle and the Temple. Midrash says that Moses composed this work on the day he completed the construction of the Tabernacle. After its completion, Moses entered the Divine clouds and was enveloped by the shadow of the LORD.

Verse four

Pinions are the “spread-out wings” of a bird. The LORD will give you special consideration when you are an instrument of His. When you are under the pinions, you have a special relationship with the LORD. He will shelter you even as the mother bird shelters her young beneath her wings.

He will cover you with His pinions, and you will take refuge beneath His wings; His truth is a barbed shield and armor.

Notes of the Psalm

The rest of the Psalm describes everything the LORD will do to ensure nothing will harm the people under his pinion. When Israel stayed true to the Sinai covenant, the LORD spread His pinions and protected them. It is when they disobeyed the LORD’s Law that the protection was removed. For today, it is imperative to follow the LORD’s Law. This adherence will bring the LORD’s protection.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

Our prayers enter the prayer conduits and can draw spiritual light from it.

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